

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 101004730

MILESTONE REPORT

Survey on current AM repair technologies for accelerator and list of possible applications

MILESTONE: M45

Document identifier:	IFAST-MS45
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 24 (April 2023)
Report release date:	31/05/2023
Work package:	WP10: Advanced Accelerator Technologies
Lead beneficiary:	RTU
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

This report presents additive manufacturing (AM) applications and strategies for particle accelerator component repair, it is divided in three parts:

- 1) State-of-art analysis: where existing AM repair technologies have been reviewed. The concept of AM repair process and strategies is also introduced, with an emphasis that AM repair process differs from AM manufacturing process and has several key factors that must be recognized. Several examples are given of successful repair cases in other industries.
- 2) A qualitative study in form of a questionnaire covering information obtained directly from the particle accelerator community. It comprises community feedback and experiences on the usage of the AM technologies and AM repairs in this field. This includes also the list of potential accelerator components (parts), which are plausible candidates for the repairs using AM technologies.
- 3) An indicative case study of a tantalum electrode repair by AM. This study includes quantitative sample characterization before and after the repair process (morphological, chemical, and mechanical analysis) and overall data of relevant repair conditions.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004730. IFAST began in May 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

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Approved by	Steering Committee		31/05/2023

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Executive summary

The report presents results of a comprehensive study on additive manufacturing (AM) applications, and technologies for particle accelerator component refurbishment and repairs. It is divided into several parts: Research on current AM repair usage in the accelerators and a study of AM repair technologies.

Current use of AM repair technologies within the accelerator community. *Concept of AM repair process has been introduced, emphasising that AM repair process differs from AM manufacturing process and has several key factors that must be recognized; such as a need for a reverse engineering, handling of the damaged components, deformations, issues of alignment and tolerances, potential need for additional pre- and post-machining, surface contamination, and finally a new material layer bonding with the substrate.*

Extensive and detailed research in publication servers and multiple general and specialised databases, revealed that there is no evidence of any identifiable case of AM repair within the accelerator realm. To validate this conclusion, a targeted questionnaire directed to the to the accelerator community at large was designed and performed.

A qualitative study *was aimed to collect existing experience and willingness to use AM technology for repairs as well as to identify potential accelerator repair objects. According to the results accelerator community is more optimistic towards production rather than repairs using AM – only 42.9% would consider AM for repairs and overwhelming 81% of respondents inclined towards component production. It is important to note, that 23.8% of respondents don't even consider using AM repairs technology as such. Naturally, a slightly pessimistic view towards AM repairs would also potentially get better with time and examples of applications. Nonetheless, **the accelerator community suggested several objects as potential demonstrators for repair, such as cavities, targets, beam dumps, electrodes, vacuum chambers and mechanical parts.** Unfortunately, almost none of the mentioned repair prospects are immediately possible without specific equipment. Therefore, further targeted studies in this direction will be needed to fully benefit from the large potential of the AM technology by the accelerator community.*

*Those **AM repair technologies**, which could plausibly be applied to the above mentioned repairs, have been reviewed and successful repair cases in other industries are presented. It is clear that not all AM technologies can, should and would be used for the repairs. Only Directed Energy Deposition, Powder Bed Fusion, cold spray AM and Additive Friction Stir processes are currently used by similar industries for component repair. One can conclude that the most promising technology is Direct Energy Deposition (DED), due to its flexibility and capability to repair large-size and complex components. The DED technology has been used in different applications in several industries and it can use either powder or wire as feedstock material.*

Conclusions. *Based on the research conducted, it is evident that none of the existing additive manufacturing (AM) technologies are currently being used for repairing accelerator components. Nevertheless, the findings suggest that AM repair technologies have the potential to be utilized in the repair of these components, although further testing is required to demonstrate their effectiveness.*

1 Introduction and Objective

The term additive manufacturing (AM) is often used synonymously with 3D printing and refers to a collection of technologies where materials are selectively accumulated to build, grow of an object layer-by-layer until a three-dimensional object conforms to its digital model [1]. AM technologies have been implemented mostly for component manufacturing. However, a layer-by-layer approach has been applicable for component repairs as well [2].

The main focus of task 10.3 research, which is reported in this deliverable, is on AM repair technologies only (not AM technologies for object manufacturing), indicating state-of-the-art approaches and successful implications in other industries which might offer a roadmap for the particle accelerator community.

Another important term in this report is particle accelerator, which is a machine that accelerates elementary particles, such as electrons or protons, to very high energies. In other words, particle accelerators produce beams of charged particles that can be used for a variety of research, medical and industrial purposes. Despite particle accelerator wide range of applications and high level of maturity and success, innovation is needed to identify and develop new sustainable accelerator technologies capable of reaching the performance required by particle physicists at an acceptable impact on society and environment [3].

All accelerator components – starting from the beginning of the beam in particle source, including components along the way as colling circuits, vacuum systems, and power sources, ending in beam dumps – all are within scope of this research.

The particle accelerator industry potentially could benefit from AM in several ways as this approach is very flexible, suitable for automation and suited for multi-material micro and macro in-situ repairs. Especially for components that are made from exotic materials, have complex manufacturing procedures, are in hostile environments or are generally prone to develop local defects.

Therefore, the objective for task 10.3 is to understand the current status of AM repair usage in the field of accelerators, to list possible AM repair applications for accelerators, as well as AM repair strategies and technologies for repairing accelerator parts, and demonstrate AM repair for accelerator components.

2 AM repairs concept and current AM repair application within the accelerators

In this chapter the concept of AM repair process is introduced, with an emphasis that AM repair process differs from AM manufacturing process and has several key factors that must be recognized. As well as will cover information on the current AM repair status within the field of accelerators.

2.1 AM REPAIR CONCEPT

AM repairs are the process where a new material layer is directly printed on the base material, which has sustained some damages and lost features. At the basic level AM repair process have some similarities with the welding repair process, which is commonly used to improve, update, and rework parts so that they equal or exceed the usefulness of the original part. Both processes can be used to fill holes, cracks, and dents in the surface. However, AM repair exceeds those applications as the near net shape feature can be restored directly on the damaged part. For example, a few damaged teeth of a gear can be restored and machined so that the part is again usable (Fig. 1). It is obvious that this approach is more sustainable and environmentally friendly than rebuilding ex-novo the full part.

Fig. 1 Additive repair process of broken gear teeth: broken gear teeth, additive repair process and finished machined part (left to right) [2]

It must be noted that in any case, component repair by AM is a more complicated process than component production by AM. Main reasons being:

- Some form of reverse engineering data is required to determine which part of the component is damaged and what geometry describes needed repair. As an example, if some defect needs to be repaired, precise information about defect location, its size and depth, etc. is needed.
- The damaged component may not match its theoretical model (new component) well at all, even in areas that are not considered a defect. Therefore, it becomes mathematically complicated to determine what the damaged volume is. In this case, the 3D scanning technique can be useful.
- Alignment of the physical component in the additive system (the machine that is doing the repair) should match with the coordinate system in the part's data in the software. If not, then the carefully determined repair geometry may not be placed correctly [4].

- Usually, some preliminary machining is needed before the repair operation to remove surface contamination and damage from surface, otherwise bonding problems between the substrate and the newly added material may occur.
- Post-machining is almost always needed, if part has critical tolerances and specification for high surface finish – which are the well-known downfalls of AM technology.
- Bonding between the base material and new material layer can be a problematic area in repairs especially if the new material layer differs from the substrate, when it is intended to improve the characteristics of the component by adding a new material layer with a different functionality to the substrate.

2.2 CURRENT AM REPAIR USAGE IN THE FIELD OF ACCELERATORS

The survey has been done to clarify current AM repair usage within the field of accelerators. For mentioned following databases were used: ScienceDirect, Scopus, Springer, Web of science, CERN document service, The Joint Accelerator Conferences Website (JACoW) and GoogleScholar. Search within these databases was done with main keywords: repair, refurbishment, maintenance, additive, manufacturing, 3D printing, accelerator.

After previously mentioned literature survey it stands out that AM applications for component manufacturing in particle accelerator field have already been studied [5]. However, it appears that for now the application of AM technology for accelerator part repair is practically non-existent, in contrast to automotive and aerospace industries, which have already adopted AM repairs in an effort to improve their product sustainability.

As investigations have shown that there are no references in literature or any publications on the topic of AM repair in the particle accelerator field, a questionnaire aimed at the particle accelerator community was launched in order to understand the reasons behind it, to identify potential knowledge gaps and potentially to collect information on the existing use AM techniques in the repairs of particle accelerator components that are not published. In addition, the authors survey potential objects for the following case/experimental study on which to demonstrate the advantages and disadvantages of the use of AM approaches in their production and refurbishment.

3 Questionnaire about AM applications and potential developments

In order to collect information on the existing use of AM techniques in the production and repairs of particle accelerator components, task 10.3 partners reached out to the particle accelerator R&D community with a questionnaire. In addition, authors seek out potential candidate component objects on which to demonstrate the advantages and disadvantages of the use of AM approaches in their production and refurbishment.

The questionnaire has been created and conducted on GoogleForms platform, distributed and circulated by weekly I.FAST project newsletter on 22.03.2022 to 290 project members from 49 participating organisations and 32 associated partners within 14 countries [6]. Further distribution of questionnaire by task leaders and coordinators has been encouraged but cannot be realistically followed.

The questionnaire was active for 3 months, after this time only 21 responses were received resulting in no more than 7.2% response rate (out of an assumed 290 mailing list members). Where the activity highlights how disinterested the particle accelerator community is in this topic at the moment or doesn't want to share their expertise in AM applications.

3.1 RESULTS: EXISTING EXPERIENCE AND FUTURE PROGNOSIS FOR AM USE

To get an overall idea of how widespread AM technology is in general – AM for component manufacturing, and repairs in any industrial application, within the accelerator community. Respondents were given a choice of three answers: they have had previous experience, they don't have had any previous experience and they don't have experience but have heard of AM use in other institutions. Out of all responses, only 9.5% of people haven't previously heard about or had any experience with AM (Fig. 2). This might lead to think, that most of accelerator community has information about AM.

Fig. 2 Particle accelerator community experience with AM

To discover accelerator community's current and future intentions on repairs with AM. Respondents were asked "Would you consider to use of AM for accelerator component production/ repairs?" with given three choices: they would now consider AM for accelerator component repair, they would not and they would consider it in future.

Fig. 3 Particle accelerator community consideration of using AM for component production and repairs

Results show that accelerator community is less optimistic about repairs than just production by AM – only 42.9% would consider AM for repairs at this moment (in comparison with 81% of AM for component production) (Fig. 3) – this points out that the repair process is an unknown principle to the community, they haven't evidence of successful examples or they truly don't believe in AM suitability for repairs. An interesting point – if no one definitely declined AM use for part manufacturing in previous question, then 23.8% don't even consider repairs for future use.

Possible AM repair applications for accelerators have been sought in the survey and listed in the following chapter.

3.2 LIST OF POSSIBLE AM REPAIR OBJECTS

Respondents, who would now or in the future consider AM for accelerator part repair (in this case – 16 respondents) were asked additional question, to elaborate on their thoughts about what parts might benefit from AM repairs. Respondents were expected to provide examples of parts that could be potentially repaired by AM. Several interesting objects were named: cavities, targets, beam dumps, ion source electrodes, vacuum chambers and drive and mechanical parts; which have been investigated in the following subchapters.

3.2.1 Cavities

To accelerate particles, the accelerators are fitted with metallic chambers containing an electromagnetic field known as cavities (Fig. 4). Charged particles injected into this field receive an electrical impulse that accelerates them [7].

The most critical part of a cavity and especially a superconducting cavity is the surface. This comes from the fact that the current flows with nearly no losses. Any contamination on the surface will give rise to extra heat and will drastically increase the losses. Due to the low thermal capacity at low temperatures even a minute heat source may provoke a large increase in temperature and superconductivity may be destroyed [8].

Fig. 4 Drift Tube Linac accelerating structure [9]

Possible defects. The surface of the cavity could be defective in several ways: from welding process or from surface coating process. Surface coating is now done by several technologies, including, vapor deposition, liquid tin dipping, multilayer sputtering, mechanical plating, electron beam evaporation, bronze processing, and electrodeposition [10].

Electropolishing is presently the preferred route for preparing the final cavity interior surface. A particular problem that electropolishing cannot address is the removal of pits near the equator welds. It is not clear at present whether pits are a result of conditions resident in the material, flaws of the material preparation prior to welding, flaws in the welding process itself, flaws in the polishing process, or a combination of these. The application of AM techniques could possibly even out the surface pits, although this is not yet researched.

Another problem arising from welding process is the burn-through – burning holes in the material if welding is done incorrectly. This is usually repaired by solid material plugs and additional welding, but could be potentially done with AM methods.

Conclusions about possible AM repairs: possible repair of coating defects, welding seams or welding process defects potentially can be done. Requires high surface finish, no inclusions and no impurities, which might be challenging with most AM methods where targeted research are needed. Defected area's reachability can be one of the main issues.

3.2.2 Targets

In a particle accelerators targets are used for research and medical applications. In research accelerators, this collision generates various types of particles and radiation, which is registered by various detectors. Targets can be solid bodies or liquid circulation systems.

Target materials are chosen based on three key characteristics: the types and abundances of rare isotopes produced; the rate at which they diffuse out of the target; and the beam power they can withstand without melting or decomposing. The three most frequently used proton-beam target materials are uranium carbide, silicon carbide, and tantalum; others include tantalum carbide, tantalum, nickel oxide, niobium, zirconium carbide and titanium carbide [11].

Target can be used only for a limited time, then it needs to be replaced and used target is stored in radiation isolated chamber. Lower-energy interactions can have long-term, negative impacts on a target, building up heat energy inside it. As the target material rises in temperature, it becomes more vulnerable to cracking. Expanding warm areas hammer against cool areas, creating waves of energy that destabilize its structure. Some of the collisions in a high-energy beam can also create lightweight elements such as hydrogen or helium. These gases build up over time, creating bubbles and making the target less resistant to damage. A proton from the beam can even knock off an entire atom, disrupting the target's crystal structure and causing it to lose durability [12].

In the case of liquid target (Fig. 5) (which is very commonly mercury) the beams bombard the target; pressure waves are generated in mercury by thermally shocked heat deposition. Cavitation is induced through the pressure wave propagation in mercury and erodes the vessel inner surface contacting with mercury, i.e. pitting damage. The eroded vessel wall is damaged by cyclic fatigue because pulsed beams strike the target repeatedly as seen in Fig. 6 [13]. Due to the service environment and elevated level of radiation, the materials used to construct the target module experience radiation and high-cycle fatigue damage. Consequently, the target module has a limited-service life and must be periodically removed and replaced, to avoid mercury leaks from targets. The target module is replaceable exclusively by remote handling equipment [14].

Fig. 5 Structure on liquid mercury target [14]

Fig. 6 Target inner wall damage due to mercury cavitation and fatigue [14]

Conclusions about possible AM repairs: targets sustain deep damage into the bulk of material (Fig. 6), therefore repair should be executed before crustal damages as a maintenance. However, AM repairs are not possible to implement for fine-tuned targets with thin multiple-layer structures.

3.2.3 Beam dumps

The purpose of a charged-particle beam dump is to safely absorb a beam of charged particles such as electrons, protons, nuclei, or ions. This is necessary when, for example, a particle accelerator has to be shut down or the beam has lost its properties and needs to be disposed before a new one is created.

Beam dumps can range from small solid metal blocks, to intricately designed assemblies to massive building like structures as the one used by CERN for the Super Proton Synchrotron, which consists of graphite, molybdenum, and tungsten surrounded by concrete, marble, and cast-iron shielding.

Beam dumps mainly sustain damage because of the heat created, since the energies of the beams to be absorbed can run into the megajoules range. For example, radiation damage from proton irradiation exhibits specific features due to the retention of hydrogen in the metal, such as hydride formation, embrittlement and nucleation and growth of hydrogen bubbles as seen in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 A 40 cm diameter tungsten beam dump from SARAF accelerator damaged after several minutes of irradiation by 4 MeV protons at a current of 6×10^{15} protons/sec [15]

Conclusions about possible AM repairs: beam dumps sustain damage deep into material. Needs special equipment and technique. As with beam dumps, large material removal before repairs is potentially needed. Most beam dumps remain radioactive for a long time – remote or in-situ repair is the only possibility if any are needed.

3.2.4 Ion source electrodes

An ion source is a device that creates atomic and molecular ions. There are many types of ion sources classified by ion type created or by ion creation method. Due to working mechanisms of ion sources – removing material to create a beam of particles, their lifetime is limited, to be more specific electrode (filament, sacrificial material) lifetime is limited and it needs periodical replaced.

In specific cases electrodes are made out of expensive and exotic materials (tungsten, tantalum) therefore disposing of used electrodes is neither economically sound nor environmental friendly.

For example, Penning Ionization gauge ion source cathodes are replaced regularly, because when the cyclotron operates, the cathodes are subjected to the impact of plasma back-accelerated ions. After a variable running time an erosion crater appears at the surface of the cathodes.

Conclusions about possible AM repairs: usually, electrodes are disposable items, but knowing that exotic materials are used for electrode production, AM repair could be an innovative application, economic and a more environmentally friendly approach.

3.2.5 Vacuum chambers

Most beam enclosing structures must maintain vacuum for beam to maintain its quality and not dissipate due to collision with air molecules. Magnet insulation chambers also must maintain a vacuum, although not as high as beam vacuum.

Components that must hold vacuum but have developed cracks and leaks are potential candidates for AM repair. Most vacuum chamber failures occur on weld seams or in places with inclusion in the raw material. Potential solution - spray metal (most likely aluminium or copper) on a chamber on which a leak developed. This could significantly increase the vacuum chamber lifetime and/or reduce the cost for the remanufacturing. CERN vacuum group is today using a varnish that is sensitive to radiation and also not ultra-high vacuum compatible. A full metal solution would be clearly an asset.

Conclusions about possible AM repairs: repairing cracks or holes in leaking vacuum chambers is a very perspective case for AM repairs, as most vacuum chambers do not need high geometrical tolerances and surface roughness. But due to high-quality requirements for porosity and inclusions, designated research in this application area would be needed because they are present with most AM methods.

3.2.6 Drives and mechanical parts

All kinds of mechanical parts that are subject to wear and tear are logical choices for repair operations. Although not every broken gear or worn shaft must be repaired – usually only economically justified parts. For example, legacy parts and custom-made components, parts from expensive and exotic materials, large and very complex parts also parts of a large assembly, that is not easily disassembled. Economic factors excluded, part repair is always more sustainable and environmentally friendly.

Conclusions about possible AM repairs: mechanical parts that wear in time, could be repaired if economically justified. However, there are not many wear and tear parts in accelerators.

3.3 CONCLUSIONS ON CURRENT AM STATUS ON ACCELERATOR FIELD

After extended survey that included and targeted questionnaire to accelerator community it stands out that AM technology applications for accelerator repair is not yet applied. Different situation is in automotive, energy and aerospace industries, where AM repair technologies have been adopted in order to improve their product sustainability.

The main conclusions of the questionnaire are that the accelerator community is not enthusiastic about AM repairs in general, according to the survey response only 42.9% would consider using AM technologies for repairs at the moment. However, respondents gave a decent number of suggested accelerator components for AM repair applications. Unfortunately, almost none of the mentioned

repair prospects are immediately possible without individual study and major parts without specific equipment (due to reachability issues). However, several mentioned objects, like cathodes, cavities and vacuum chambers can show great potential by using AM repair technologies. That led to collect accelerator requirements within the following chapter (Table 1), which should be considered in AM repair applications.

By summing up: according to initial research that consisted of current AM repair status investigation, and extended research with the survey, feasible AM repair technologies should be collected by showing AM repair options to the accelerator community. Also, it was noted that probably positive examples are missing as evidence for accelerators, therefore AM repair technology should be demonstrated as a case study by using the accelerator components. The research is in progress and continuation is done in the following report.

3.4 PARTICLE ACCELERATOR COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Particle accelerators are complex, with tight tolerances, fine-tuned machines, where component production and especially repairs pose many engineering challenges for supporting technologies. Major physical constraints are described in Table 1.

Table 1 Physical properties affecting particle accelerator components

Requirement	Value	Unit	Source	Significance for components
Vacuum	$< 10^{-12}$	mbar	[16] [17]	No pores, no contamination, no defects, structural integrity.
Voltage	$< 120 - 330$	kV	[18] [19]	No internal defects, low surface roughness, no surface damages.
Magnetic field	< 16.5	T	[20]	Correct choice of magnetic/nonmagnetic materials, shielding
Temperature	$1.9 - 2273$	K	[20]	Choice of material.
Radiation	$< 10\ 000$	Gy per year	[21]	Choice of material, part location and shielding
Frequency	$3 - 12\ 000$	MHz	[22]	Very low surface roughness
Electrical conductivity	$5.8 \cdot 10^7$	$\Omega^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$	[23]	Pure materials, dense structures, no surface contamination, low roughness

Of course, not all aforementioned specifications applies to every single one of accelerator components all the time – they might vary from case to case, but the specific requirements have been mentioned for holding vacuum, high voltage, wide temperature range, radiation etc. It could be concluded that the strict and unusual demands of component properties could be one of the reasons why AM is not very widespread in accelerator community and should be considered in further developments.

4 AM repair technologies

This chapter is dedicated to the investigation of which AM technologies have the potential to be used in particle accelerator component repair, including a short analysis of dominant metal AM technologies. Several examples are given of successful repair cases in other industries. In order to maintain focus and narrow down the subject, the main emphasis has been on metal AM technologies as most of the particle accelerator components are made of metallic materials.

4.1 REPAIR TECHNOLOGIES

A variety of technologies, equipment, and materials are used in the repair of parts via AM. Each method and machine have advantages and drawbacks – characteristics such as speed, costs, versatility, manufactured part geometrical limitations and tolerances, as well as mechanical properties and visual appearance.

There are several technologies that are already now used in component repair – directed energy deposition, powder bed fusion, cold spray AM and additive friction stir deposition. Examples of successful repair cases have been reported in the next sections.

4.1.1 Powder bed fusion for repairs

Powder bed fusion is the most well-known AM technology for metal part production. In this process, a powder bed is created by raking powder across the work area. The energy source (electron beam or laser beam) is programmed to deliver energy to the surface of the bed melting or sintering the powder into the desired shape. Additional powder is raked across the work area and the process is repeated to create a solid three-dimensional component by many layers. In the end, the part is removed from the powder, cleaned from residual powder, and post-processed [24].

Research has been done using this method by Zghair [25] who introduces an additive repair design approach, with focus on Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) technique, and investigates mechanical properties and the bonding force between the damaged components and the added repaired volume, whilst introducing several distinctive repair strategies for powder bed fusion process (Fig. 8).

There is also research in accelerator field, but it is not described as repair, although the concept is almost the same. There is a two-part component called beam dump. To perform its functions, the beam dump should have a front portion, facing the beam, composed of bulk dense copper to effectively stop the incoming protons, and a second back portion where the cooling system acts to cool down the front. In this case the back portion cooling channels are printed with LPBF on top of solid copper disc (Fig. 9) [26].

Fig. 8 Powder bed fusion repair process, building directions and planes. a) Flat surface, one building stage. b) One oblique surface, one building stage. c) Two oblique surfaces, two building stages. d) Two oblique surfaces, two building stages [25]

Fig. 9 Side view of the CAD design and manufactured cooling channels on top of copper disc (as an example: the new part is manufactured on top of an existing object by creating a mono structure, that demonstrates repair feasibility and possibilities by using LPBF) [26]

Similar work done by Smelov [27] on possibility of restoring blades while repairing gas turbine engines parts by LPBF (Fig. 10). Based on this, Siemens Energy (Germany) is announcing a new digital repair chain using “Hybrid” LPBF that makes it possible to add new features to gas turbine blades [28].

Fig. 10 Gas turbine engine blade repair by selective laser melting. a) model of damaged blade b) welding part to build plate c) lowering blade into powder bed d) pre-filling powder bed with powder e) and f) repaired parts [27]

The main limitation of PBF repair technology is that the build surface needs to be flat and parallel to the build platform (in the plane with x-y axis). Otherwise, the first layer of powder thickness will not be uniform and will lead to severe build defects. The common method to do this is to fix the repairable component to build platform, then grind the top of the repairable part parallel to the built platform bottom plane, lower all these fixtures in the powder bed, and rake powder across fixture until it is all covered. Due to this, there is no possibility to incorporate support structures for upcoming builds if needed, as now there is only the possibility to build upwards and support only on powder that limits overhangs (max 45 deg.). It is now evident why this method is not one of the favourites in part repairs.

4.1.2 Directed energy deposition for repairs

Directed energy deposition (DED) is a group of AM processes that add material alongside the heat input simultaneously. The heat input can either be a laser, electron beam, or plasma arc. The material feedstock is either metal powder or wire [29]. In both systems, build material is conveyed through a nozzle onto the build surface. A laser beam is used to melt build material and base material (or

previous layer) to obtain monolith structure and create the desired shape. This process is repeated to create a solid three-dimensional component layer by layer [24].

There is some promising research in railway industry – restoration of worn rails by laser powder deposition (Fig. 11) [30]. Where the deposition zone contained a total of six deposition layers. There were visible signs of microcracks in the first layer near the rail-deposition interface. Micropores also were detectable in all the layers. The overall evaluation indicated that this is a promising rail repair technique. However, to achieve a perfectly repaired rail, the microcracks and micropores that developed must be minimized or eliminated. Preheating before repair process and isolating the rail substrate during heat treatment are suggested solutions that will require further studies in the future [30].

Fig. 11 Rail repair by DED a) Worn rail; (b) repaired rail, front view; (c) repaired rail, upper view, showing the longitudinal tool path; (d) a thin slice from the repaired rail [30]

Other research of laser powder deposition for repairing the surface defects of spline shaft to improve wear resistance, shows how composite coatings were fabricated on the spline shaft surface by laser cladding with TiC reinforced Ni based powder (Fig. 12) [31]. A very notable detail must be noted from this work – after AM processes the finished surface was obtained by grinding process.

Fig. 12 Repair of spline shaft by laser cladding [31]

A procedure to repair a mold insert for use in the casting of aluminum cylinder heads for internal combustion engines by wire arc AM deposition technology and subtractive processed on single machine has been developed and analyzed in recent research (Fig. 13) [32]. Overall, at the end of the first life of the mold insert, the results highlighted that the AM repair-based approach could allow potential savings and offer environmental benefits, compared with the mold insert being machined

from a massive workpiece. It must be noted that in this repair, very extensive machining operations were conducted after AM to obtain specified surface roughness and geometric accuracy.

Fig. 13 Wire Arc AM for mold repair. a) original component b) component with damaged faces removed c) component with added metal layer d) cross section after AM process [32]

The research about DED technology shows there are many possible issues and defects due to thermal influence and technology properties. Common defects for all DED systems are [33]:

- Poor surface finish;
- Porosity, cracks, non-metallic inclusions and incomplete fusion;
- Lack of geometrical accuracy;

For now, DED is the most popular AM technology for part repairs. The key benefits of DED over other techniques are:

- It creates a stronger bond between base and added material;
- less restrictions on the repairable component sizes than with PBF;
- repair equipment has multi axis movement;
- In-situ repair opportunities.

The benefits of the stronger bond are obvious. A multi axis and in-situ repairs means that repair can be made of many angles and is not restricted to one plane. The downside of the technology is that the structure to be renovated will be of relatively simple construction and will require surface post-processing.

4.1.3 Cold spray for repairs

Cold spray additive manufacturing (CSAM) is a derivation of cold spraying – one of thermal spraying methods which are a class of surface coating technologies. CSAM uses heated high-pressure inert gas to accelerate metal powders through a nozzle above the critical velocity for deposition onto a substrate. Upon impact particles deform, creating high strains and localized plasticization of the material so that a combination of both mechanical interlocking and metallurgical bonding can be achieved thus creating a 3D component [34].

A comprehensive review of cold spray AM has been published by Yin [35], with several examples of cold spray repair applications (Fig. 14 and Fig. 15).

Fig. 14 Cold spray AM repair process of bearing cap [35]

Fig. 15 Cold spray AM repair process of flange – damaged part, part after spraying, part after machining [36]

In cold spraying used for repairs, there are concerns about bonding forces (delamination is very common with cold spraying), work hardening and higher residual stress in the deposit due to increased plastic deformation of the particles. Research shows that residual stress in the deposits can be released through post-spray annealing. Additionally, deposits normally have worse mechanical properties – as lower ductility, lower electrical conductivity, and lower thermal conductivity when compared to bulk materials or fusion-based AM. Defects such as micro-pores and inter-particle boundaries are commonly found in deposits. These defects are caused by insufficient particle plastic deformation and poor inter-particle bonding during deposition [35].

Similar to other restoration techniques, the feedstock for CSAM cannot be deposited on the damaged component directly because of the complex surface topography, and the potential for the contaminated surface of the damaged area to compromise bond strength. Pre-machining on the damaged zone is necessary to reconstruct the damaged surface. Surface treatment is then conducted on the reconstructed surface with milling, grinding, or grit-blasting to prepare a clean and level

surface which is suitable for CSAM. As well post machining is also required as CSAM is struggling to produce sharp edges, perfectly flat surfaces and high tolerance geometries [35].

4.1.4 Additive friction stir deposition for repairs

Additive friction stir deposition (AFSD) process is an emerging solid-state technique which works on principles of AM and friction stir engineering. AFSD enables near-net shaping with the help of site-specific deposition. It involves a hollow non-consumable rotating tool through which raw material in the form of powder or solid rod is fed. The fed material inside the hollow tool rotates with the tool shoulder. As the tool/fed material meets the substrate, frictional heat generates. The temperature of fed material increases resulting in its yielding and extrusion in the space between substrate and tool head.

One niche application of AFSD is the structural repair of components for the aerospace and defence industries, in which load-bearing components may suffer from corrosion, wear, or other damages. Griffiths et al. [37] explored the through-hole and groove filling of AA7075 plates and showed that AFSD was effective at filling the entire volume (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16 Friction stir AM repair for 1/4" hole [37]

Sufficient mixing was observed between the deposited material and the sidewall of the feature; as a result, the interface was indiscernible with a gradual change in microstructure. In that preliminary investigation, no optimization strategy was employed for process parameters and the scanning path, and inadequate repair quality was sometimes observed in deeper portions of the filling. In the ongoing work by the same group of authors, such defects are shown to be largely eliminated by improving the repair strategy, e.g., by tuning the tool head rotation rate and dwell time. The repaired aluminium plates (after removing the excess deposited material from AFSD) exhibit decent static and fatigue performance [38].

The downsides for friction stir repairs are that the repaired structure can be very simple, the repair will require surface machining and mechanical forces are involved in the process where a repaired object can be damaged. All mentioned leads to conclude that AFSD is not the best choice for accelerator applications.

4.2 AM REPAIR CHALLENGES

AM repair challenges that are known within AM and have been noted after the survey from the accelerator community as well, are concerned with part properties – porosity, surface roughness, grain structure (Fig. 17), density, mechanical strength. All the aforementioned challenges are well known in AM applications and therefore are being researched intensely in all industries.

Right now, AM technologies like LPDF, state of art reached 99.99% or really close to that, dense structures in multiple applications, however, knowing that the AM is a complex, dynamic and metallurgical process there would be present some minor internal imperfections and especially surface roughness as it is shown in (Fig. 17). As can be seen most of the defects are on the surfaces or close to it (Fig. 17 c)) and that is an area where AM technologies should focus on. Nevertheless, on the market are available several technologies (for example from Rösler) that can make post-processing for rough AM-built structure.

Fig. 17 Typical defects of the Selective Laser Melting parts: a) spherical and irregular porosity, b) open porosity [39] c) surface defects and d) grain structure [40]

The specific problem that particularly stands out for AM repair is the accessibility issue – repairing parts, especially in accelerators are closed structures, like cavities. Where without specially designed equipment it would be hard to reach the damaged areas. The same, reachability issue would be present for local post-processing, and machining that are applied after AM repair. However, those challenges can be minimized step by step, beginning with testing AM repairs for easily reachable areas by testing the feasibility and then improving reachability by modifying equipment.

4.3 CONCLUSIONS AFTER AM REPAIR TECHNOLOGY STUDY

It can be concluded that not all AM technologies can be used for repairs. Only DED, PBF, CSAM and AFSD processes are now used in industries for component repair. It must be noted that in any case component repair by AM is a more complicated process than component production by AM.

The main reasons are the need for some reverse engineering, theoretical and real part dimension comparison to construct geometry that will need to be added. Additionally, the component must be reliably and precisely placed in the machine that will do the repairs – so that added geometry aligns with existing geometry. Usually, some pre- and post-machining is needed – this makes AM repair process more of a hybrid type process. DED is the favourite and is used in the majority of cases due to versatility and equipment availability.

The AM repair process is a special case for the particle accelerator industry as accelerator components operate in specific work environments: ultra-high vacuum, high voltage, extremely low temperatures etc. (requirements are included in Table 1.) This calls for low porosity, good mechanical properties, high tolerances and excellent surface finish for parts that routinely need to be made from exotic materials of the highest purity. Those all are possible reasons why in particle accelerators AM is now used mainly in proof-of-concept component manufacturing and not yet in repairs. Although in some specific accelerator industry is similar to others - aviation, aerospace, nuclear energy etc. industries.

5 Conclusions

The main conclusions of the “Survey of AM applications and strategies for repairing components by AM” are that particle accelerator technologies have high standards and requirements, due to a very specific work environments, for example – high vacuum, high voltage, extremely low temperatures etc. This calls for low porosity, good mechanical properties, high tolerances and excellent surface finish for parts that routinely need to be made from exotic materials of the highest purity. Those requirements can be challenging for AM repair technologies, mainly due to surface roughness and undesirable internal defects. However, several specific accelerator requirements are very similar to those of other domains – vacuum requirements are similar to aerospace, radiation effects to the nuclear energy industry etc. There are several technologies that are already now used in component repair – directed energy deposition, powder bed fusion, cold spray AM and additive friction stir deposition. Other fields as aerospace and automotive have already implemented AM repairs, yet in particle accelerators AM today is being used only for component manufacturing.

The main conclusions of the qualitative study in form of a questionnaire addressed to the particle accelerator community are that the accelerator community is not yet enthusiastic about AM repairs, according to the survey response rate. However, the possibilities of this technology have been acknowledged as 3/4 of the respondents would consider AM for part production but less than 1/2 for repairs. This fact is supported by all the examples of AM parts in the particle accelerator industry reported in previous chapters and by the fact that demonstrator for AM repairs was hard to find. One can assume that the slightly pessimistic view of AM repairs would also get better with time and examples of applications and successful examples.

Can conclude that a specific case study as a demonstrator for the accelerator community is needed for further research, to show AM technology's feasibility. That is achieved and reported within the Task 10.3 deliverable report.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
3D	three dimensional
AFSD	additive friction stir deposition
AM	additive manufacturing
AMIT	Advanced Molecular Image Technologies
CAD	computer aided design
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
CIEMAT	El Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas
CNC	computer numerical control
CSAM	cold spray additive manufacturing
DED	directed energy deposition
EDS	energy dispersive spectroscopy
JACoW	the joint accelerator conferences website
LHC	large hadron collider
LPBF	laser powder bed fusion
PBF	powder bed fusion
PIG	penning ionization gauge
SEM	scanning electron microscopy
SLM	selective laser melting